

RESHUFFLING OF STATIONS AMONG SCHOOL HEADS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF TANTANGAN: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

Mirasol C. Olegario

*Magon Elementary School, Division of South Cotabato
Master in Management Student-East West Mindanao Colleges Inc., Kamasi,
Ampatuan, Maguindanao, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

A school environment with a negative school climate, an authoritarian management approach, and incomplete collegiality may negatively affect the quality of the teacher. The study aimed to explore the reshuffling of stations among school heads in the municipality of Tantaran. This research used qualitative research which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations. The participants of the study are 9 school heads who are being reshuffled or transferred to the new station for the school year 2023-2024. A semi-structured guide survey questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information and responses from the participants of the study. Thematic analysis was used to process the responses of the participants. On the unexpected and sudden changes in their new station as school head, the following themes are generated based on the responses of the teacher participants of the study, adjusting and adapting to the new environment, prioritizing tasks, and open communication. On the new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations that may occur in their new station, the following themes were generated based on the statement of the teacher participants of the study, salient information from stakeholders, and the right direction in making decisions. On their mechanism in seeking out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations, teamwork, and cooperation. Interestingly, on how they manage their emotions and reactions in ambiguous situations, Value of Understanding Code of Professional Ethics.

Keywords: *Reshuffling, School Head, Stations, Tantaran,*

INTRODUCTION

Public schools and school systems, as they are presently constituted, are simply not led in ways that enable them to respond to the increasing demands they face under standards-based reform. Further, if schools, school systems, and their leaders respond to standards-based reforms the way they have responded to other attempts at broad-scale reform of public education over the past century, they will fail massively and visibly, with an attendant loss of public confidence and serious consequences for public education. The way out of this problem is through the large-scale improvement of instruction, something public education has been unable to do to date, but which is possible with dramatic changes in the way public schools define and practice leadership.

All these systems are interconnected, which in turn creates even more variables as these open systems reshape constraints and possibilities. This never-before-seen dynamic requires us to use a systemic approach and engage in complex decision-making. We all say that leadership is just not about the title or power; Leaders need to be bold, brave, daring, open, vulnerable, and sensitive, to lead wisely. However, the true test of effective leadership in an organization is not how they perform in good times, but more in times of crisis; which has left many of us feeling frightened and uncertain, Baron, L., Rouleau, V., Gregoire, S., & Baron, C. (2018).

Many people have experienced frustration and stress during the pandemic and many schools have struggled on how to continue in these challenging times. Therefore, school leaders need to stand up and do the right things for both their personnel and partly for the educational system.

Leadership can also be described as the act of guiding or influencing other individuals or groups. Experienced school leaders will come to know that flexibility in their approach is one of the key components to being an effective leader, especially this time. While it is important to stick to their core values, leaders must adapt to ongoing situations and be ready to take the initiative to navigate what is present. We cannot predict the future, instead, it is important to support our vision with a set of flexible approaches. In recent times, the ongoing global pandemic has brought challenges to everyone in their unique circumstances, Bennett, N., & Lemoine, G. J. (2014).

The Division of South Cotabato particularly in Tantaran 1 district implemented the Rationalization Plan where school heads are transferred to another school for more or less three years staying in their current school, thus this study was conceptualized to explore the Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, Ambiguous (VUCA) environment of the school head in their new station.

Research Questions

The study focuses on the leading schools in a Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, Ambiguous (VUCA) world. Specifically, the study was carried out with the following objectives;

1. What are the unexpected and sudden changes in your work in your new station?
2. What is the new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations that may occur in your new station?
3. What is your mechanism for how you seek out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations?

METHODOLOGY

The study uses qualitative research, particularly phenomenological research design. Which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the lives of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations, Wa-Ambaleka (2018).

The participants of the study were eleven (11) school heads in Tantanagan District I. The inclusion criteria will be a current or incumbent school head in schools that was reshuffled regardless of their plantilla position this school year 2023-2024.

RESULTS

On the unexpected and sudden changes in their new station as school heads. The following themes were generated by the unexpected and sudden changes in their new station as school heads, **adjusting and adapting to the new environment, and prioritizing tasks and open communication.**

On the new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations that may occur in their new station. The themes were generated in terms of new information and perspective to better understand uncertain situations that occur in their new station such as; **salient information from stakeholders and the right direction in making decisions.**

On their mechanism in seeking out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations. The theme that was generated on the mechanism of seeking diverse out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations is **Teamwork and cooperation.**

On how they manage their emotions and reactions in ambiguous situations. In terms of the ambiguous situation, the school head participants shared their views and thoughts on the **Value of Understanding Code of Professional Ethics**.

DISCUSSION

On the unexpected and sudden changes in their new station as school head

In education systems like the state government level and public education at the local level, concerning districts and schools that employ teachers, recruitment and retention policies have a direct impact on their ability to fill the desired number of teaching fields.

The following themes were generated by the unexpected and sudden changes in their new station as school heads, **adjusting and adapting to the new environment, and prioritizing tasks and open communication**.

The first theme generated was to **adjust and adapt to the new environment**. Where school head participants shared their thoughts as:

“As a neophyte School Head, it required me lot of adjustment, especially to the new work environment, specifically the teachers, learners, and parents. But as mandated with the function, I willingly accepted the challenge. The first week will be more in roaming around school and a thought observation. I prepared also a feedback mechanism to cater to expectations and ways forward”, Participant 1, Male, Mr. J, Principal 1;

“Common changes that usually occur in our station are changes in weather conditions, additional workloads, new designations, promotions, student misbehavior, reshuffling of school heads, misbehavior, and many more. Whenever I face unexpected changes in my working environment, I first take a moment to understand the situation and look into the positive and negative impact of the sudden change. Then, I prioritize my tasks and communicate with relevant individuals to ensure a smooth transition and come up with a good decision and solution”. Participant 7, Female, Mrs. M, Head Teacher II

The result of the study is related to the statement of Gawęda 2018 states that the school head should be a partner for the employees and for the students a support and an individual who is involved in recognizing their needs and eliminating all didactic and educational problems. Singular school heads are motivated to work and learn, promote appropriate behaviors on the school's website, and involve parents in school life, determining the principles and rules of cooperation.

The second theme that was generated was **prioritizing tasks and open communication**.

School heads, as key leaders in the country's education system, are indispensable in the realization of the government's aim to provide schoolchildren with quality basic education.

In regards to the generated theme of prioritizing tasks and open communication. The school head participants share their ideas state that;

*As a neophyte School Head, it required me lot of adjustment, especially to the new work environment, specifically the teachers, learners, and parents. But as mandated with the function, I willingly accepted the challenge. The first week will be more in roaming around school and a thought observation. I prepared also a feedback mechanism to cater to expectations and ways forward. **Participant 1, Male, Mr. J, Principal 1;***

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*“Handling sudden changes in the workplace or school may sometimes be challenging but I think my optimism and adaptability made me cope with it. As to how well I handle sudden change, I can say that I am still a novice since it is just my third year as a school head. As to how I handle it, I make sure that I have gathered the necessary information and understand the reasons for change before making any decisions or taking any action”. **Participant 8, Female, Mrs. S, Head Teacher II;***

*“For me, I can address unexpected changes by communicating effectively with my colleagues or the teachers and even with my superiors. Moreover, embracing the changes as an opportunity for growth is the best approach for it may develop new skills and learn new ways of working”. **Participant 8, Female Mrs. S, Head Teacher II***

The result of the study is related to the statement of Barola, R., C, & Digo, G., S. (2022). School heads may influence or improve and increase their levels of knowledge, practice, and professional engagement which leads to an enabling and supportive environment for effective teaching and learning to happen even amid a global educational crisis.

In addition, School heads, as key leaders in the country's education system, are indispensable in the realization of the government's aim to provide schoolchildren with quality basic education. Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education

Act of 2001, states that a school head is a person responsible for administrative and instructional supervision of a school or cluster of schools.

On the new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations that may occur in their new station

Modern organizations are going through continuous changes and have to deal with high uncertainty due to the still-growing worldwide competition and a quickly changing economic climate.

The themes were generated in terms of new information and perspective to better understand uncertain situations that occur in their new station such as; **salient information from stakeholders and the right direction in making decisions.**

As the school heads participants share their thoughts about this matter;

*“In every station you are assigned, you encounter differences and adjustments in the school culture. I asking for salient information from the community, the teachers, and the learners about what they are expecting from me, and how are we (The school head, Teachers, learners, community, and stakeholders) best improve the school for the learners and learning strategies as well as physical outlook of the school. Dahil una sa lahat ay bata. “Bansang makabata, Batang makabansa”. **Participant 3, Male Mr. A, Teacher In-Charge, Teacher III***

*“When I was transferred to the new station, I always seek information or ask the previous school head about the operation of the school, the people in the school and about the relationship between and among the school community. Moreover looking beyond, the immediate circumstances and considering how the situations fits into the larger context can help us gain a deeper understanding of uncertain situation at hand”. **Participant 8, Female Mrs. S, Head Teacher II***

*“When I was transferred in my new station, I always seek information, communicating with the teacher and PTA official and stakeholders. Collaborating with them, making informed decisions. By following these steps I can effectively manage uncertain situations in my new station”. **Participant 9, Male J, Head Teacher I***

*“No one is perfect, I have my weaknesses and limitations. With this, most of the time, I need to seek out new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations. By doing so, I am always guided in the right direction in making decisions”. **Participant 4, Male Mr. N, Principal II***

The result of the study conforms with the study of Boesso, G. and Kumar, K. (2019) that the power and legitimacy that managers

associate with a stakeholder group cumulatively are the most important determinant of how managers go about prioritizing competing claims. The results also provide some evidence to the effect that the greater the priority accorded to a stakeholder group, the greater the efforts aimed at engaging the stakeholder groups (as evidenced by the voluntary disclosures made in the annual report).

The second theme generated was **the right direction in making decisions.**

Decision-making is the most crucial aspect of educational management. Research suggests that decision-making is one of the salient factors upon which the survival of any organization is based.

The school head participants share their thoughts about the direction in making decisions as;

“No one is perfect, I have my weaknesses and limitations. With this, most of the time, I need to seek out new information and perspectives to better understand uncertain situations. By doing so, I am always guided in the right direction in making decisions”. **Participant 4, Male Mr. N, Principal II;**

“Aside from our regular SLAC meeting I openly discuss and seek suggestions and connect with the program coordinators as the situation comes along”. **Participant 5, Female Mr. K, Principal I;**

The result of the study is parallel with the study of Gawęda, L. (2018) in which principals who rated their job satisfaction and efficacy as high gave their superintendent a high rating on their decision-making potential. Decision-making is considered an indispensable component of the management process and the headmaster's life is filled with making decisions after decisions. They see decision-making as their central job. Since decision-making involves one's competence, his personality makes up, besides administrative orientation. For that, the head of the institution should possess a balanced type of personality which helps him to accommodate all queries when a particular situation allows them to arise.

On their mechanism in seeking out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations

Problem-solving in complex situations or systems requires an appropriate and reliable understanding of the problem.

The theme that was generated on the mechanism of seeking diverse out diverse perspectives and input to better understand complex situations is **Teamwork and cooperation.**

The school head participants shared their views as;

“I think one way is to have a prioritization strategy which includes creating a task and scheduling the task. By doing so, there is a smooth operation of all the activities in school. Moreover, as much as possible, I should always communicate with my colleagues to increase productivity and get things done as expected. Lastly, to gather diverse viewpoints and inputs, I need to consider many things in making decisions. When making decisions, I don’t only consider a single tree rather, I need to consider the whole forest”. **Participant 4, Male Mr. N, Principal II;**

“As a school head, we always consider a variety of viewpoints. We involve our people/ teachers in the decision-making process that will allow for a broader image of perspectives and ideas which in turn can lead to better informed and more balanced final choices”. **Participant 5, Female K, Principal I;**

“As a leader, you cannot solve or give solutions alone for whatever problems may arise. You need to talk with the people involved. As for how to prioritize each area, you need the pros”s and cons”s and the benefits of each decision to be made”. **Participant 6, Female Mrs. E, Head Teacher II;**

“To ensure that I will be able to gather diverse viewpoints, I make sure that everyone understands the reasons and purpose of the situation. I communicated to them the pros and cons of the situation and allowed them to collaborate in the decision-making process. This is to ensure that everyone feels included and valued in the process and that their contributions are accepted”. **Participant 7, Female M, Head Teacher II’**

“I think in terms of prioritizing methods, It should be based on urgency and weight. Of course, in making such a decision we need to have a collective idea and weigh everything as to how much such an idea helps us in coping with the challenges and making solutions to the problem”. **Participant 8, Female Mrs. S, Head Teacher II, and**

“As a school head, I will be able to involve various methods such as open forums, and diverse representation in decision-making bodies and to make sure everybody can understand the complex situations and community engagement. By prioritizing these, we can ensure we gather diverse viewpoints and input, fostering inclusivity and a deeper understanding of complex situations”. **Participant 9, Male Mr. J, Head Teacher I**

The result of the study is anchored on the statement, that Manzoor et. al (2011), state that the team can be defined as a group of individuals who work collectively to achieve the same purposes and goals to provide an excellent quality of services. Teamwork can enable the members of the team to have a higher level of emotional security, self-confidence, and the ability to plan and decide with others positively. Also, it

helps in creating a healthy work environment with workable agendas, creative activities, positive strategies, and values. On the other hand, the absence of teamwork concepts and strategies can lead to occupational failure, disappointment, low morale, and poor productivity which threatens the entity of the organization. The employees who work in an organization that does not have a strong concept of teamwork, usually fail to deliver the expected results and to achieve the goals and visions of that organization. The presence of the teamwork concept is a necessary rule to help the employees work together towards common aims and goals creatively.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Adjusting and adapting to a new environment, whether it's a new job, a new team, or a new situation, is essential for success. Here's a structured approach to prioritizing tasks and fostering open communication in a new environment.

By prioritizing tasks effectively and fostering open communication, you can enhance productivity, collaboration, and overall success in any environment. These principles apply whether you're working on individual projects, leading a team, or contributing to a larger organizational effort.

As a school head, being adaptable to change is a valuable skill in today's dynamic and fast-paced world.

Making decisions effectively requires a combination of critical thinking, sound judgment, and clarity of purpose.

Lastly, Teamwork and cooperation are essential for achieving common goals and fostering a positive work environment

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented. The school head may continue the rapport with the stakeholders and promote shared governance. The school head may continue open communication with the teachers, and stakeholders to promote camaraderie. The school head may continue the teamwork and cooperation to poster the school of peace. That this study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture quantitatively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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